

Impact of Technology in Modern Business

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Abstract

Once upon a time people were talking about Stone Age, but now people speak about global village and global room. This change has taken place because of technology. The total income of the country is being increased. There are lot of merits simultaneously demerits also are there. Technology brings people closer and reduces the paper work too.

Technology also creates unemployment amidst the people. For example harvesting once upon a time people were harvesting with hand but now even small formers use machine. Like this there are lot problems also involved.

Prologue

We are living in the modern world, wherein things are being modernised and digitised and the use technology is becoming inseparable from any business. For about thousands of years technological innovation the application of knowledge about tools, materials processes, and techniques to problem solving has had profound effect on our lives as possible, some time positively, and other times negatively. Technological innovation has been a central component of the warty in which new economic value is created by permitting people and companies to use existing resources more efficiently, as well as to come up with products and services that meet people's needs in ways that were not met before.

In order to meet evolving and shifting customer expectations and demands, the business men need to get grips with multi-channel shopping behaviour of today's shoppers. Shoppers everywhere access Smart phone, tablets etc., in order to avail things for their use therefore the seller have to adopt themselves according to the need of the shoppers.

Technological Changes

Adoption of new technologies has improved the quality of service offered by several organisations. The integration of computers and telecommunications has revolutionised communication sector. The influence of internet on the service organisations like travel, banking, education, financial services, insurance etc., is total. With advent of national or even global electronic delivery systems, they have totally transformed the scope of the business, Further; they facilitate

reengineering activities such as delivery of information, execution of orders, settlement of claims and payments, etc. These developments have enhanced the service standards by permitting the creation of centralised customer service departments and replacement of men by machines.

Background of the Study

Physical and digital world opens up a new business opportunities and challenges that were hard to imagine just decade ago. But then now the new decade opened up a way for digital world. Long ago only the land lords were using machined for harvesting baddy but now the situations is different because even the small farmer who won small piece of land is using harvesting machine. More over people were not allowing the machine for harvesting at present people had forgotten hand harvesting. We can understand very clearly the changes that had taken place in the lives of the people. Once upon a time we were talking about paperless work at present we converse about labour less work. The foreign countries have excess workers especially from India. The main reason is technological growth that had taken place.

Technology and Business

We are living in a competitive world; where in each and every minute new technology is coming in. According to the needs of the customer the business men have adopt new technology. People are not ready to see the benefits and durability instead they look for convenience and the cover cum attractiveness. Technology and business can't be separated now because for each and everything we depend on machines like production, packing, transport, billing, grading etc.

Information Technology

The study or use of systems, especially computers and telecommunications for storing, retrieving, and sending information is called information technology.

Information technology can change the way business compete. At present people buy things not by seeing the quality but by the prestige. It doesn't end with things even for education medicine and so many necessities are included. In no time the goods reach the customer, we can book tickets, film, pay tax, pay electricity bill, book car, and bye food, medicine we can sell things, deposit money in the bank online. Everything is done by information technology.

Technology is a Connecting Source

The rapid speed of technology development and rising adoption of mobile digital devices on global scale, such as Smartphone and tablets, have a profound transforming impact on consumer behaviour retail business at lager.

Technology is the biggest linking source among manufactures retailers and the customers. Before the technology came to existence there was big gap amidst them but now technology brought them closer. For example door delivery, we can order food and other items by zomoto or swiggy etc.,

here there are choices for consumers which was not there earlier. Technology is the part and parcel of every aspect of business today.

Technology Opens up New Data Sources

All the technological Innovations, platforms and applications present a tremendous potential in the form of access to previously untapped sources of data. Data that now can be collected, example at the point of sale, and analyzed to obtain a more complete view of the customer o the one hand and to improve and enrich the overall customer experience of the other hand.

The customers themselves become an advertiser for the product because now we have the facility of blogs wherein they can write about the product which will be seen worldwide by the customers. There can be both positive and negative elements which will help us in the future to bring about the change in the product and in dealing with the customers.

Merits and Demerits of Information Technology

Though information technology makes things easy it also has some demerit

Merits

Transmission of message becomes quicker both audio and video, lot of information can be saved and paperless work provides information needed to any task, save time brings people closer.

Demerits

The invention of face book, twitter, snap chat, messenger and other social media are destroying the student life, people became lazy, people are becoming dependable because we order everything online and People lose money.

Advertisement

The other important factor that decides the business is advertisement. When we think of tooth paste Colgate comes first it is because of the advertisement.

Merits

Introduces a new product I the market, Expansion of the market, increased sales, fights competition, enhances good-will, educates the consumers, elimination of middle men, better quality products and supports the salesmanship.

Demerits

Adds to cost, undermines social values, confuses the buyer, encourages sale of inferior products, encourages monopolistic control, pushed our small businesses reduce small business employment and manipulated people to spend outside of their purchasing allowance.

Technology and Customer Satisfaction

Immediate response

The technology should enhance the relationship of customer for this immediate response is must. By responding immediately the time of customer is being saved.

Active listening

Active listening is the important aspect which will bring the buyer again and again to the product. They should feel that the arte listened and cared. Active listening may give hope to the customer.

Seamless communication

Only by the true communication we can win over the customer. If the customer comes to know that we are not truthful we lose the customer. First of all the good will of the product should be kept up.

Customer empowerment

At present majority of the people prefer a self-service option. We need to concentrate on empowering our customers with self-service tools that allow them to do things like pay or solve problems themselves. When the customers are empowered they will bring in others automatically.

Anticipate problems

We can't give assurance that all our customers will be satisfied. Some may leave a negative note. It has to be rectified before it is revealed. The customer should be called and be given reward.

Epilogue

The young generations are looking for the latest technology, according to their needs and taste we need to update our mode of business, lest we lose our customers. Now more than ever, customer satisfactions are higher, if the needs are not fulfilled customers may cease to use our product. If the customer is given superior customer experience the buyer may return again and again. Building customer loyalty also brings in new customers and recurring revenue.

Technology has impacted the business to the full. Technology and business can't be separated now because both became indispensable. Business process operation has entered a new phase of accelerated transformation. New technology helps employer to attain the objectives. Advanced technology brings innovation which play as a back bone of organization. Though there are many problem because of technology like unemployment and small scale business are being thrown out still the technology helps people and nation to march ahead to attain the goal.

References

1. The Network is your customer- by David Rogers
2. The Search: How Google and its Rivals rewrote the rules of business and transformed our culture- by John Battelle
3. Empowered: Unleash Your Employees, Energize your customers and transform your business- by Josh Bernoff
4. Bricklin on technology- by Dan Bricklin.
5. Digital Impact: The two Secrets to Online Marketing success by- Vipin Mayer, Geoff Ramsey